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Tsunami Hazard Map for Cádiz (Spain) derived from a Local-Scale Probabilistic Tsunami Hazard Assessment (S-PTHA) and Science-Based Participatory Decision-Making

Prepared by **IHCantabria**

for

UNESCO-IOC EU DG ECHO COASTWAVE 2.0 PROJECT

*Strengthening and Upscaling the Resilience of Coastal Communities in the North-East
Atlantic and Mediterranean Region to the Impact of Tsunamis and Other Sea Level-
Related Coastal Hazards Project (DG ECHO CoastWAVE 2.0)*

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Disclaimer

The work proposed in this document is intended to improve tsunami preparedness but does not guarantee the safety of people. The authors assume no responsibility for damage to persons or property caused by a tsunami.

Legal notice

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DG ECHO CoastWAVE 2.0 project main working team in Spain:

KEY STAFF

Ignacio Aguirre Ayerbe*	<i>*Project Coordinator and corresponding author. Disaster Risk Management Specialist.</i>
Mauricio González	<i>Coastal Engineering Specialist and Tsunami Expert.</i>
María Merino	<i>Integrated Coastal Zone Management Specialist.</i>
David Galán	<i>Tsunami Hazard Analyst.</i>
SUPPORT STAFF	
Albert Gallego Jiménez	<i>Programming support.</i>
Patricia Bueno	<i>Administrative, financial and communication management.</i>

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1. Background

Tsunami preparedness is essential to minimise the negative consequences of tsunami impacts on coastal communities. Achieving the strongest and most effective preparedness for these events is one of the main concerns of the Tsunami Team and the Coastal Management and Engineering Group of **IHCantabria**. For this reason, and in line with the **UNESCO-IOC** vision on tsunami preparedness, prevention, response and recovery, the following STATEMENT OF WORKS AND WORKPLAN is submitted aimed at supporting the activities that the UNESCO-IOC will carry out in Spain, together with other Member States of the ICG/NEAMTWS, in the framework of the EU DG ECHO funded project **DG ECHO CoastWAVE Phase II: *Scaling-up and Strengthening the Resilience Coastal Communities in the North-East Atlantic and Mediterranean Regions to the Impact of Tsunamis and other Sea level-related Coastal Hazards.***

Based on a strong understanding that community awareness and preparedness to respond to tsunami warnings are essential components of an end-to-end tsunami warning system, DG ECHO CoastWAVE project Phase II aims to scale-up and further strengthen the resilience of vulnerable coastal communities in Northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean regions to tsunamis and other sea-level-related hazards. The overall impact sought by the project is to reduce risk, increase safety and enhance the resilience of vulnerable coastal communities to sea level-related disasters in NEAMTWS countries. DG ECHO CoastWAVE project Phase II is articulated in four components:

- Component 1: Build and strengthen tsunami hazard assessments, risk knowledge, risk communication, and decision-making capacities.
- Component 2: Scale-up and expand Tsunami Ready in selected NEAM countries.
- Component 3: Enhance and densify early warning, detection, monitoring, and alerting systems.
- Component 4: Enhance dialogues with Emergency Responders, Decision Makers on High Impact Low Probability (HILP) tsunami events within a multi-hazard context to improve strategies and effective decision-making capabilities.

IHCantabria successfully implemented the Phase I of the EU DG ECHO CoastWAVE Phase I project in Spain. The project counted on the involvement and support of several related stakeholders at all administrative levels in Spain. Among them were the main stakeholders related to tsunami disaster risk management in Spain. At the national level, the Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE), which also acts as UNESCO-IOC Tsunami Warning Focal Point (TWFP), the National Seismic Network Department of the Sub-Directorate General for Monitoring, Warning and Geophysical Studies of the Geographic National Institute (IGN), which also acts as UNESCO-IOC National Tsunami Warning Centre (NTWC) and Tsunami Warning Focal Point 2 (TWFP-2), and the National Oceanographic Institute (IEO), which acts as UNESCO-IOC Tsunami National Contact Point (TNC). At the Autonomous Community of Andalusia, the regional Directorate General of Emergencies and Civil Protection (DGEPC of the Junta de Andalucía). At the municipal level, the Municipality City Council of Chipiona, Local Police, Civil Protection, Red Cross, Civil Guard, and several municipal civil organizations and the population in general.

Building on the achievements and experience gained in the implementation of the DG ECHO CoastWAVE Phase I project, the implementation of the DG ECHO CoastWAVE Phase II project in Spain aims to scale up and expand the implementation of the UNESCO-IOC Tsunami Ready Recognition Programme (TRRP) in the country, thereby strengthening tsunami preparedness at municipal, regional and national levels. To this end, a probabilistic approach to tsunami hazard will be incorporated, along with enhanced science-based participatory decision-making, capacity building in tsunami risk management, reinforcement of preparedness in complex urban environments, and the establishment

of dialogues with key stakeholders and users involved in coastal planning and resilience. This approach seeks to integrate tsunami risk management into a multi-hazard planning context, including partnerships with existing resilience initiatives such as MCR2030.

Within this multi-hazard and coastal resilience framework, the project also intends to capitalize on the work developed for application to other potential threats, such as coastal flooding or earthquakes, by (i) incorporating additional potential hazards into the conceptualization of evacuation plans and maps and (ii) leveraging and adapting structure of the local tsunami emergency plan for use in managing other hazards.

The objectives of the DG ECHO CoastWAVE Phase II project will be achieved through the implementation of the twelve indicators of the UNESCO-IOC Tsunami Ready Recognition Programme (TRRP) and the corresponding recognition procedures outlined in UNESCO-IOC Manuals and Guides No. 74 (hereafter referred to as MG74). The entire process will be integrated in accordance with Spain's legal and regulatory framework, taking into account additional municipal initiatives, and carried out in close coordination with key stakeholders and decision-makers responsible for tsunami risk management across various administrative levels in Spain.

This document constitutes the deliverable called **Tsunami Hazard Map for Cádiz (D2a)**, which is the second deliverable of the project. Deliverable 2 also includes the first financial report (D2b), which will be submitted as a separate document.

The following sections describe the applied methodology, the outcomes, and the participatory decision-making process designed to support the tsunami emergency officer of the municipality of Cádiz in determining the tsunami hazard zone for emergency and evacuation planning.

2. Introduction

Cádiz is a coastal municipality and the capital of the province of the same name, in the Autonomous Community of Andalusia. It has a population of approximately 112,000 inhabitants (INE municipal census for 2023). This number can increase by around 25% during the peak tourist season, such as during the Cadiz Carnival (a Festival of International Tourist Interest), the summer months and other local celebrations.

The city and municipality of Cadiz have a complex geographical structure due to its location (Figure 1). Cádiz is located on a peninsula almost entirely surrounded by water and connected by an isthmus (tombolo) to the so-called Isla de León, which itself is separated from the mainland by a narrow channel known as Caño de Sancti Petri. Its location gives it unique characteristics both in its configuration and surroundings. The area is embedded within a landscape of dunes, channels, salt marshes, and beaches, forming the Bay of Cádiz—a natural area of high ecological value.

Figure 1. Municipality of Cadiz location.

Cádiz is exposed to tsunami events due to its proximity to the SW Iberian Peninsula seismic and tsunamigenic area (Figure 2). This area, located about 400 km from Cape San Vicente, triggered the event known as the “Lisbon earthquake and tsunami” in 1755. Although at that time the Spanish coast was much less populated than it is today, the death of more than 1200 people has been documented in Cadiz and Huelva due to this tsunami.

Figure 2. Source [García-Orellana et al., 2006]. Plate-tectonic setting of the SW Iberian Margin, at the boundary between the Eurasian and African plates (inset) and shaded relief map of the SW Iberian Margin, based on SRTM-3 for land topography and GEBCO for bathymetry. White arrows depict plate convergence motion (4.5–5.6 mmyr⁻¹) from the NUVEL1 model [e.g., Argus et al., 1989]. Grey dots represent earthquake epicentres from the Spanish IGN catalogue for the period between 1965 and 2003. High magnitude historical and instrumental earthquakes that occurred in the SW Iberian Margin after the 1755 event are represented by the star symbol.

Today, an event of similar magnitude would have tragic consequences in Cádiz due to the high degree of urban development, population growth, and the significant commercial, touristic, fishing, and industrial activities in the area. These include one of the most important ports in Spain and southern Europe, notable for its strategic location and diverse operations, cargo (including vehicles), passenger transport, and fishing, as well as a high volume of traffic that accommodates various types of vessels.

In addition, its geographical complexity directly results in a very challenging emergency landscape in the event of a tsunami. The city has only three main exits: two cross the sea, and the third runs parallel to the coastline, entering the marshy area of the Natural Park of the Bay of Cádiz.

In summary, the location of the municipality of Cadiz, exposed to potential tsunami impacts and characterized by a complex geographical environment for emergency management in the face of sea-related coastal hazards, combined with a large population, diverse activities and critical infrastructures (including a major port), represents an extremely relevant case study for this project. Scaling up the TRRP to a scenario like this one will expand the range of community types to which this approach can be applied, thereby providing a valuable example for other communities, cities and municipalities with similar characteristics.

The methodology developed in this study, focusing on tsunami hazard for emergency and evacuation mapping, is based on the concept of multi actor “science-informed participatory decision-making” for tsunami management (Aguirre-Ayerbe et al., 2025).

3. Seismic Probabilistic Tsunami Hazard Assessment (S-PTHA)

Tsunami hazard assessment is the first step towards a better understanding of the actual risk faced by the municipality, as it identifies the areas that may be affected to varying degrees depending on the intensity of the hazard. It also addresses the first indicator of the TRRP, “Tsunami hazard zones are mapped and designated,” which falls under the Assessment section of the programme (Assessment indicators of the UNESCO-IOC Tsunami Ready Recognition Programme (TRRP).Figure 3).

Figure 3. Assessment indicators of the UNESCO-IOC Tsunami Ready Recognition Programme (TRRP).

This assessment and its corresponding indicator are essential for the effective development of the other indicators, particularly those related to assessing the exposure of people and assets, preparing evacuation maps, developing local tsunami emergency plans, installing warning systems, and promoting public education and awareness.

The method applied to assess tsunami hazard and generate the corresponding maps for the municipality of Cádiz is based on numerical modelling using the GPU-based Tsunami-HySEA code (Macías et al., 2017) and a probabilistic approach grounded in the regional NEAMTHM18 model (Basili et al., 2021). This approach quantifies the probability of exceeding a specified inundation intensity at a given location within a defined time period by integrating the modelled hazard from all considered tsunami scenarios.

The following sections describe the process undertaken to apply this methodology and generate the tsunami hazard maps for Cádiz.

3.1 S-PTHA Methodology

The methodology has been divided into four stages (Figure 4):

- A. Collection, preparation, and organisation of the baseline information for the execution of the numerical model.
- B. Selection of sources for local PTHA analysis.
- C. Modelling Tsunami generation, propagation and inundation.
- D. Development of tsunami hazard maps.

Figure 4. Methodological framework used for tsunami hazard assessment. * POI: Point of interest; ** PS: Predominant seismicity, BS: Background seismicity, SBS: Secondary background seismicity, PSMar: Predominant seismicity in the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, PSSlip: Predominant seismicity due to slippage (Basili et al., 2021).

3.2 Compilation, preparation, and organisation of baseline information for the PTHA:

3.2.1 Task A-I. Topobathymetry:

A system of nested numerical grids has been implemented, starting from a global/regional scale with moderate spatial resolution (on the order of ~ 1 km) down to a local scale with high spatial resolution (5 m), allowing the development of detailed inundation maps at the municipal level.

The external bathymetric information (elevation = 30 metres deep) was obtained from the EMODnet¹ (The European Marine Observation and Data Network) database, supplemented by the GEBCO² (Gridded Bathymetry Data) database. GEBCO data has been used in the coarsest grids (levels 0 and 1), EMODnet has been used in the intermediate grids (levels 2 and 3), and finally, the detailed grid has been completed with nautical charts (level 4) (Figure 6).

The local bathymetry for the municipality of Cádiz was obtained from nautical charts 443 of the Nautical Chart Web Catalogue – Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina (IHM), Spain (*Catálogo Web Cartas Náuticas del Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina*)³, with a resolution of 1:50,000. As for the topography, a digital terrain model (DTM) from the *Instituto Geográfico Nacional* (IGN)⁴ was used, with a resolution of 5 metres.

¹ <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>

² https://www.gebco.net/data_and_products/gridded_bathymetry_data/

³ [Catálogo Cartas Náuticas del Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina](#)

⁴ <https://centrodedescargas.cnig.es/CentroDescargas/index.jsp>

The highest-resolution grids have been adjusted to account for tide levels in the study area. Tide variability was incorporated into the numerical model as a boundary condition by modifying the topobathymetry accordingly. To determine the relevant tide levels, data from the Bonanza 2 tide gauge, located near the study area in the province of Cádiz and recording at one-minute intervals from 1992 to 2017, were used in combination with the Puertos del Estado tidal scheme (Puertos del Estado, 2019), as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Main sea level references derived from the complete Bonanza tide gauge record (data recorded since 1992).

Since the grids are referenced to mean sea level (NMM), a maximum astronomical high tide of +186 cm (calculated as PMMA 359 cm – NMM 173 cm) and a minimum astronomical low tide (BMMI) of –154 cm was considered. Accordingly, seven sets of final grids were generated, corresponding to the tide levels: –1.5 m, –0.5 m, mean sea level, +0.5 m, +1.5 m, and +1.86 m. The full set of grids is presented in Figure 6, with the last one (Grid04_5m) adjusted for each scenario based on the specific tide level considered.

Among the different tide levels analysed, +1.5 m was selected as it combines a significant sea level rise with a higher probability of occurrence than the +1.86 m level, corresponding to the maximum astronomical high tide recorded, while still resulting in extensive inundation. This is illustrated by the cumulative distribution function shown in Figure 7, based on 20 years of hourly astronomical tide data.

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of nested grids in the probabilistic study

Figure 7. Cumulative distribution function (CDF) of astronomical tides. The main percentiles are indicated. The +1.5 m condition is close to the 95th percentile, while the maximum observed high tide (+1.86 m) represents a more extreme and less frequent event.

3.2.2 Task A-II. POI selection

As noted earlier, the NEAMTHM18 regional tsunami hazard model (Basili et al., 2021) serves as the basis for this Seismic Probabilistic Tsunami Hazard Assessment (S-PTHA) developed in Cádiz. The model provides annual occurrence rates for seismic sources within the study area—that is, the estimated frequency with which an event is expected to occur in a given year. These rates are then used to calculate the probabilities of different tsunami scenarios impacting the area of interest. All this information refers to the so-called Points of Interest, POIs throughout the North-East Atlantic, Mediterranean and Adjacent Seas region, known as the NEAM region.

Figure 8. Point of Interest (POIs) distribution of the NEAMTHM18 model (image: EPOS Tsunami TCS⁵)

Figure 9. Location of the POIs selected for the study

In this case, three points near the study area were selected based on potential tsunami arrival directions to adequately represent the variability and the most relevant tsunamigenic scenarios for assessing the impact on Cádiz. This selection ensures that all events potentially affecting the points of interest (POIs) are included in the analysis. The identifiers for these sources are nea00292, nea00300, and nea00307 (Figure 9)

⁵ <https://hazard.tsunamiata.org/?dataset=NEAMTHM18>

3.2.3 Task B. Selection of tsunami sources for local implementation of the PTHA

Tsunami hazard analysis requires the simulation of a large number of earthquake and tsunami scenarios due to the considerable natural variability of seismic events and their effects. Seismic events vary significantly in their characteristics and do not generate tsunamis of equal extent. However, simulating hundreds of thousands or even millions of scenarios may be unfeasible due to time and computational resource limitations.

For this reason, a subset of scenarios that contribute most significantly to the hazard in the study area is selected. These priority scenarios are identified through a process known as *disaggregation*.

The disaggregation process was conducted following the methodology described by Tonini et al. (2021) and Gibbons et al. (2020), using the NEAMTHM18 regional model results as a reference at three POIs located near the target area (see Figure 9), which are located in the vicinity of the target area. This process allowed the classification of all possible scenarios according to their relative contribution to the tsunami hazard at these locations, quantified in terms of average annual occurrence rates.

Once the most relevant scenarios have been identified, i.e., those contributing most significantly to the hazard curve at the POIs, it becomes possible to define the desired level of accuracy for the local hazard representation. This is done by comparing the original hazard curve at the POI, derived from the regional model, with the new curve obtained using only the selected scenarios. A high degree of similarity between both curves confirms that the subset of scenarios sufficiently represents the tsunami hazard at the study site.

Specifically, scenarios were selected whose associated sources contribute the most to the exceedance probabilities for key wave height thresholds (0.3, 0.5, 1, and 4 m). The selection was made by applying a 99% accuracy criterion, meaning that the cumulative contribution of these scenarios reproduces at least 99% of the original hazard curve from the regional model at the POIs. As shown in the curves in Figure 10, extracting this subset leads to a slight underestimation of relatively low tsunami heights (<0.3 m MIH). To mitigate this effect, the weights assigned to each selected scenario were renormalised so that their cumulative probability remains proportionally consistent. This renormalisation process ensures that the total probability is preserved, thereby reducing the risk of underestimating hazard levels for lower tsunami heights.

Figure 10. Hazard curves extracted for the three NEAMTHM18 POIs closest to the study area (nea00292: lon=-6.575, lat=36.592; nea00300: lon=-6.437, lat=36.442; nea00307: lon=-6.408, lat=36.278). The axes are labelled as follows: PoE (Probability of Exceedance) and MIH (Maximum Inundation Height). The dashed vertical lines indicate the selected wave height thresholds (0.3, 0.5, 1, and 4 m). The dashed red line (“Total”) represents the original cumulative hazard curve at the Point of Interest (POI), showing the probability that a given inundation height will be exceeded in 50 years. The blue line (“99%”) corresponds to the hazard curve based on the subset of selected scenarios before renormalisation; it closely overlaps with the orange line (“W/corr”) is the renormalised curve obtained after adjusting the scenario weights to preserve the total probability and correct for underestimation at lower inundation level.

The disaggregation analysis, after integrating the POI data and removing duplicate entries (i.e., the same event occurring at more than one selected POI), resulted in a list of seismic scenarios. For each case, the earthquake parameters required for tsunami simulation are provided, along with the event occurrence rate according to the NEAMTHM18 regional model.

This assessment identified a total of 8,760 seismic events or scenarios. Among these, 7,686 are classified as Background Seismicity (BS) sources and 1,074 as Predominant Seismicity (PS) sources. In terms of spatial distribution, 6,972 events correspond to local sources—including 4,748 BS and 2,224 Secondary Background Seismicity (SBS) events—while the remaining 1,788 events are attributed to distant sources, comprising 714 BS events, 181 PS events, and 893 PSSlip events (see Figure 11 and Table 1). For a comprehensive description of the BS and PS sources, refer to Basili et al. (2021).

Figure 11. Left: Spatial distribution and classification of the seismic sources incorporated in the probabilistic tsunami hazard assessment, categorized by seismicity type. Right: Zoomed-in view of the Gulf of Cádiz and Southwest Iberian Margin region. The color scale represents the cumulative annual occurrence rates at each location.

Seismicity class	Source type	Number of scenarios
BS	Local	4748
SBS	Local	2224
BS	Distant	714
PSMar	Distant	181
PSSlip	Distant	893

Table 1. Summary of seismic sources used in the probabilistic tsunami hazard assessment

3.2.4 Task C. Generation and propagation of the tsunami using a numerical model

This task involves simulating tsunami scenarios based on the seismic scenarios selected through the disaggregation process. For this purpose, the GPU-based numerical model Tsunami-HySEA (Macías et al., 2017) was employed to simulate the complete tsunami process, including generation, propagation, and coastal inundation. In the generation phase, the model applies Okada's analytical solutions (Okada, 1985) to compute seafloor deformation from fault parameters, which are then used to estimate the initial sea surface displacement and generate the tsunami wave. The model can combine multiple fault planes to represent complex rupture scenarios during the generation phase, as Tsunami-HySEA allows the definition and integration of multiple seismic source parameters to simulate realistic seafloor deformation and tsunami generation processes (Macías et al., 2017).

High-resolution flood maps at the municipal level in Cádiz were generated using a system of nested numerical grids with varying scales and resolutions, incorporating different tide levels as described in Section 3.2.1 and illustrated in Figure 5 and Figure 6. This approach enables the simulation of tsunami events from a global/regional scale, with moderate spatial resolution (~1 km), down to the local scale, with high spatial resolution (5 m).

Regarding tsunami wave propagation, simulations apply different durations based on source location: 4 hours for local sources and 12 hours for distant ones, reflecting the travel time required for the tsunami wave to reach the area of interest.

For each simulated scenario, if the flood depth exceeds 1 cm, the maximum values of three tsunami intensity parameters—flow depth, velocity, and momentum flux (calculated as the product of flow depth and the square of velocity)—are recorded at each point of the 5 m resolution grid.

The outcome of this process is a multidimensional dataset that, for each scenario, includes the probabilities or occurrence rates alongside the maximum values of the three tsunami intensity parameters at each of the approximately 13.5 million points of the 5 m resolution grid covering the Cádiz study area.

3.2.5 Task D. Post-processing (development of tsunami hazard curves and maps).

The final task of the process involves the computation of hazard curves at each point of the 5 m resolution grid, by combining the results of the flood simulations with the occurrence rates of the associated scenarios. These curves represent the probability of exceeding various tsunami intensity thresholds over a defined time period, which in this study is set to 50 years.

To construct these curves, different intensity thresholds are considered (e.g., 1 m, 2 m, 3 m for flow depth). For each threshold, the maximum value reached in every simulation is evaluated, and if the threshold is exceeded, the occurrence rate of that scenario is included in the cumulative exceedance probability. This procedure is repeated for all thresholds and all scenarios to obtain the full hazard curve at each grid point.

In this study, flood depth was selected as the reference intensity parameter for hazard assessment. However, similar hazard curves can also be generated for other intensity measures stored in the dataset, such as flow velocity and momentum flux.

To account for epistemic uncertainty, multiple alternative models were considered for each simulated seismic scenario. This ensemble approach enables the computation of a range of hazard curves that reflect the variability and uncertainty inherent to the modeling process. As illustrated in Figure 12 hazard curves are generated not only for the mean value, but also for several percentiles of the

epistemic distribution (2nd, 16th, 50th, 84th, and 98th percentiles), providing a more comprehensive characterization of the tsunami hazard.

Figure 12. Example of a tsunami hazard curve for flow depth at a specific point in Cádiz (highlighted with a red dot on the map of Cádiz). The curve shows the probability of exceeding different flow depth thresholds over 50 years, represented for several percentiles of epistemic uncertainty (2nd, 16th, 50th, 84th, and 98th).

Based on these curves, various hazard maps are generated by taking horizontal cross-sections at predefined Average Return Periods (ARPs), corresponding to specific probability or rate values along the hazard curves. As with the hazard curves, maps are produced for the mean estimate and for several percentiles of epistemic uncertainty (2nd, 16th, 50th, 84th, and 98th percentiles). The resulting maps include both the inundation extent, defined as the set of land grid cells where the expected flow depth exceeds 1 cm for a given ARP, and the expected flood depth at each grid cell under specific sea-level conditions, as derived from the hazard curves (see18 Results section).

3.3 Results

This section presents the various maps obtained for a sea level tide scenario of +1.5 m. This tide scenario was selected as it combines a significant sea level rise with a higher probability of occurrence than the maximum astronomical high tide recorded, as described in Section 3.2.1.

The following are examples of hazard maps derived from the model outputs for Average Return Periods (ARPs) of 2,500, 5,000, 10,000, and 25,000 years, considering epistemic uncertainty percentiles of mean, 2nd, 16th, 50th (median), 84th, and 98th.

Two figures compile the results: Figure 13 displays the flood extent maps, while Figure 14 presents the corresponding flood depth maps.

Inundated area; ARP: 2500 years

Inundated area; ARP: 5000 years

Figure 13. Hazard maps showing flooded areas for different percentiles of epistemic uncertainty, calculated for return periods of 2,500, 5,000, 10,000, and 250,000 years.

Flowdepth [m]; ARP: 2500 years

Flowdepth [m]; ARP: 5000 years

Figure 14. Hazard maps showing flood depth (in metres) for different percentiles of epistemic uncertainty, calculated for return periods of 2,500, 5,000, 10,000, and 250,000 years.

4. Participatory Workshop on Tsunami Hazard Zoning for Emergency and Evacuation Planning in Cádiz

This chapter summarizes the outcomes of a participatory workshop, designed, organised and coordinated by IHCantabria in collaboration with the municipality of Cádiz, held on June 26, 2025, with key stakeholders and decision-makers involved in tsunami risk management in Cádiz. The workshop aimed to facilitate open discussion and collective decision-making regarding the delineation of tsunami hazard zones to be used in emergency response and evacuation planning. The process was grounded on the probabilistic tsunami hazard assessment results, ensuring that scientific evidence informed the zoning decisions. The collaborative approach sought to integrate technical expertise with local knowledge and priorities, enhancing the relevance and applicability of the hazard zones for effective disaster risk reduction in the municipality.

The main objective of the workshop was to support the identification of the tsunami hazard zone, based on the scenarios derived from the probabilistic analysis (S-PTHA). The selected hazard zone will serve as the foundation for the development of the local tsunami response plan, as well as for evacuation planning. The workshop was designed as a decision-support tool for stakeholders responsible for tsunami risk management in Cádiz.

The session was structured in two main parts. The first part presented the methodology used for the tsunami hazard analysis and its application to the municipality of Cádiz, along with similar examples from other parts of the world.

The second part focused on the impacts associated with the different inundation scenarios and led into a guided discussion session. This provided an opportunity to address questions raised during the presentations and to open a valuable debate on the various considerations for defining the tsunami emergency and evacuation planning zone, based on the probabilistic hazard analysis (See agenda in Table 2).

During the presentation, it was emphasized that, after reviewing all the information provided in the workshop, including the report with the methodological approach, the results, and the discussion and suggestions from participants, decision-makers are expected to define a tsunami hazard zone based on the probabilistic analysis, to be used for emergency and evacuation planning, within a 10-day timeframe. This decision is critical, as it forms the foundation for the upcoming tsunami risk assessment, preparedness, and response activities.

Time	Description	Presenter
9:00	Participant registration	
9:20	Opening remarks	Civil Protection Coordinator and Chief of Local Police
9:30	Introduction to the workshop	Ignacio Aguirre Ayerbe - IHCantabria
9:40	Introduction to <i>DG ECHO CoastWAVE 2.0</i> project	Ignacio Aguirre Ayerbe - IHCantabria
9:55	S-PTHA methodology	Ignacio Aguirre Ayerbe - IHCantabria
10:30	Other International case studies	María Merino - IHCantabria
10:40	Coffee break	
11:00	Decision-making support: Impacts by ARP and Uncertainty Levels	Ignacio Aguirre Ayerbe - IHCantabria
12:30	Guided discussion with participants	Ignacio Aguirre Ayerbe and María Merino - IHCantabria
14:00	Closing remarks	Civil Protection Coordinator and Ignacio Aguirre Ayerbe

Table 2. Agenda of the workshop: Participatory Workshop on Tsunami Hazard Zoning for Emergency and Evacuation Planning in Cádiz, held on June 26, 2025.

Figure 15. Overview of the room during the presentation on the probabilistic tsunami hazard assessment in Cádiz, showing some participants and the presenter.

4.1 The workshop

The workshop began with an introduction to the DG ECHO CoastWAVE 2.0 project, followed by a presentation of the methodology used for the Seismic Probabilistic Tsunami Hazard Assessment (S-PTHA) in Cádiz. The methodology applied is the one detailed in this report, which constitutes Deliverable 2 of the DG ECHO CoastWAVE 2.0 project. A summarized version of the same content, in Spanish, will be included in the Local Tsunami Emergency Response Plan for Cádiz. After presenting the methodological framework, participants were shown the resulting inundation zones for the municipality, corresponding to average return periods of 2,500, 5,000, 10,000, and 25,000 years, with particular emphasis on the 84th and 98th percentiles of epistemic uncertainty. This Figure 16 serves as an example of the preliminary tsunami inundation maps that were presented during the workshop.

ARP 10000yr & Pc 84th

ARP 10000yr & Pc 98th

Figure 16. Flood extent and depth for a 10,000-year return period, corresponding to the 84th (left) and 98th (right) percentiles of epistemic uncertainty.

The consequences associated with each of the previously presented inundation scenarios were then introduced. For each scenario, these consequences were expressed through estimates of the inundated area, the number of exposed buildings and critical facilities, and the affected population. The information was presented using maps (to provide a spatial overview), tables (to offer a detailed data analysis), and graphs (to illustrate trends in relation to different return periods and percentiles of epistemic uncertainty).

Periodo de retorno	Probabilidad 50 años (%)	Percentil	Área (km ²)	Población expuesta	Edificios expuestos	Edificios críticos expuestos
500	10	50	0.18	1020	27	0
		84	0.50	2156	50	0
		98	0.87	3248	66	0
1000	5	50	0.43	1929	46	0
		84	1.32	4771	105	1
		98	2.25	7270	278	4
2500	2	50	1.43	5225	127	1
		84	3.28	12199	670	18
		98	5.77	38468	1892	46
5000	1	50	2.56	8737	382	9
		84	5.76	38262	1702	44
		98	7.46	55155	2910	58
10000	0.5	50	3.83	18084	888	23
		84	7.13	49094	2594	54
		98	7.87	61172	3265	65
25000	0.2	50	5.62	35089	1518	44
		84	7.76	58114	3124	62
		98	8.10	64560	3460	70

Figure 17. Example map showing the inundated area, exposed buildings, and critical facilities in zones 1 and 2, based on the 84th percentile (Pc84) and an average return period (ARP) of 10,000 years. Bottom: Summary of inundated areas and exposure of population, buildings, and critical facilities for different combinations of return period, their equivalent 50-year probability of occurrence (in percent), and various levels of epistemic uncertainty.

Finally, the discussion session featured a structured, guided debate based on a set of predefined questions concerning the implications of selecting return periods and percentiles of epistemic uncertainty of varying magnitudes. These choices directly influence the extent of the area designated for emergency and evacuation planning. The debate addressed, in particular, the potential risks associated with over-evacuation in the case of events less severe than the planning scenario, the human and logistical resources required under different planning options, and the relevance of critical infrastructure as a determining factor in decision-making regarding the delineation of the evacuation zone. The session concluded with an open round of individual contributions, allowing participants to share their views and considerations. In summary, the guided discussion resulted in 12 key insights, including suggestions, reflections, and observations, as follows:

1. It is suggested to consider vertical confinement as an option within tsunami emergency planning.
2. It is recommended to opt for a high return period (10,000 or 25,000 years) due to its significant difference from a 5,000-year period, accompanied by at least an 84th percentile uncertainty level.
3. It is proposed that, when selecting the hazard zone for emergency and evacuation planning, the population that could be rescued or the amount of exposed population the municipality can manage should be estimated.
4. It is advised to adopt a scenario-based flooding approach with high return periods and high uncertainty percentiles.
5. It is noted that zones 3 and 4, according to the preliminary zoning presented, are the most challenging regarding tsunami exposure and evacuation difficulties.
6. It is emphasized to consider population density and the distribution of vulnerable groups when deciding the hazard zone for emergency and evacuation planning.
7. It is recommended to include critical city zones, including critical buildings, in the selection of return period and uncertainty percentile combinations used to determine the flood zone.
8. It is suggested to base the decision on the zone for emergency and evacuation management on either a 10,000-year return period with an 84th percentile or a 98th percentile uncertainty with return periods between 5,000 and 10,000 years.
9. It is proposed that it may be more relevant to first consider a high uncertainty percentile (98%) and then determine the return period.
10. It is emphasized that resources should not limit the selection of the flood zone for emergency and evacuation planning; if resources are insufficient, planning should be adjusted to include necessary resources for high return periods and high uncertainty percentiles.
11. It is recommended to realistically consider available and acquirable resources based on a realistic estimation in planning.
12. It is observed that there is a tendency to favour adopting high return periods and high epistemic uncertainty levels, which aligns with the population's likely understanding, as they are accustomed to associating tsunamis with large-scale, intense events—based on the narratives of the 1755 event.

4.2 The adopted tsunami hazard zone

After reviewing all the information presented during the workshop, including the report on the methodological approach, the results, and the discussions and suggestions from participants, the primary decision-makers in tsunami risk management for the municipality of Cádiz decided to adopt the tsunami hazard zone corresponding to the average return period of 25,000 years, with the 98th percentile of epistemic uncertainty. This decision was communicated to the project coordinator via email on July 11, 2025.

The map corresponding to such tsunami inundation zone is provided in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Map showing the tsunami inundation zone based on the combination of an ARP of 25,000 and the 98th percentile of epistemic uncertainty.

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